

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE GENDER TINT OF LIFE: HEALTH AND CAREER

Ilynykh S.,

PhD in Sociological Sciences, professor

Head at the Department of Sociology,

Novosibirsk State University of Economics and Management

Tevlyukova O.,

PhD candidate in Sociological Sciences, associate professor,

associate professor at the Department of Sociology

Novosibirsk State University of Economics and Management

Rovbel S.

PhD candidate in Economic Sciences, associate professor,

associate professor at the Department of Sociology

Novosibirsk State University of Economics and Management

Abstract

The article analyzes a person's life in the context of gender. Gender is constructed by social practice, reinforced by social norms and social stereotypes. In daily routine activities, gender is continuously reproduced. The specificity of the structure is that it strictly prescribes to men and women the performance of certain actions based on their gender, builds a hierarchy of social relations. Gender stereotypes are "hidden" guidelines for actions that determine the choice of behavior patterns for men and women. It always has consequences that are hidden from representatives of socio-demographic groups. Gender behavior manifests itself in all spheres of life, especially in the field of health care and career building. Studies show that men are less likely to seek medical help, even if they have health problems, and demonstrate risk-based behaviors. Such practices related to health are driven by gender stereotypes. In the field of career, it is shown that there are ideas about which area of activity is a priority for men and which for women. The results of an empirical study are presented that reveal ideas about the limitations for men and women in various spheres of life. The influence of gender stereotypes is shown on the example of work as pilots and police officers for women, or kindergarten teacher for men. The article provides examples of word formation and gender behavior from the point of view of gender analysis.

Keywords: gender, gender stereotypes, gender concepts, health, risk, career.

Introduction.

The first articles on gender issues appeared about twenty years ago. Research began to be carried out in various areas of scientific knowledge – sociological, philosophical, psychological, economic, historical, linguistic ([1], [4], [6], [7], [8]). A separate direction has appeared – gender studies. Although the interpretation of the basic concept of "gender" was very heterogeneous, from a simple loan translation of the English "gender" to "socio-gender" relations, it became clear that from now on it is no longer possible to consider men and women only as representatives of large socio-demographic groups, as representatives of the biological sex. There was a need to study how the real system of interactions between men and women is built in all spheres of life.

It turned out that these interactions turn out to be "loaded" with subtle, but invariable constants – gender. Over time, researchers have discovered that gender is not just sex, it's a social construct in relation to one gender or another. It is constructed by social practice, reinforced by social norms and social stereotypes. In daily routine activities, gender is continuously reproduced. Gender practice is so "natural" that it is almost not questioned. However, the specificity of gender constructions, is that it strictly prescribes for men and women the performance of certain actions in accordance with gender, rigidly hierarchizes relationships. As a result of the action of gender, gender inequality has become firmly established, which manifested itself in a variety of areas.

Purpose of scientific research. To study on empirically how gender specificity is embodied in real life social practice, in the behavior of men and women.

Research methods. To empirically illustrate the gender nuance in the lives of men and women, the results of an empirical study conducted by the author in 2018-2019 are used. The sample is multistage: regionalized, random, quota (N=771, questionnaire survey).

Research results.

Health. According to the results of a study of residents of the city of Novosibirsk, conducted in 2019 (N=771, questionnaire survey, multi-stage sample: regionalized, random, quota), it turned out that 40% of men do not take any action to maintain their health. For comparison: there are 1.5 times less women (27%).

Such practices of self-preservation of men's health can be explained by involving the theory of gender. The reason is rooted in the period of early socialization, when the boy is told that he should always be strong, not complain like a girl, not cry, decide everything on his own. These gender stereotypes then complicate the lives of both men and women, as they are like "rigid corridors" that oblige them to follow them. As a result, even being deeply in need of medical care, a man does not go to doctors, which ultimately leads to a reduction in life expectancy.

The risk behavior of men can be explained by evolutionary concept of gender differentiation by V. A. Geodakyan, which the author of the article also considers to be one of the most significant in gender theory. According to his concept, evolutionarily young signs in

most cases occur in men. The scientist states that men are more willing to take on new, requiring search, non-standard tasks (therefore, they can perform them in rough outline), and then women bring the solution of familiar tasks to perfection. Men are innovators in any business. They were the first to master all professions, sports, and even knitting. But the role of the avant-garde in susceptibility to disease and social vices also belongs to men [5].

Thus, the risk behavior of men fits well into the framework of the concept of V.A. Geodakayana. Currently, society is in a situation of operational localization of the epidemic threat, it is men who more often violate the prescribed norms of behavior. Quite often you can see the following picture: of couples walking together, a woman more often has personal protective equipment, and a man does not.

Career. Each gender, in accordance with gender stereotypes, should do its own thing. Therefore, there are ideas about which area of activity is a priority for men, and which are for women. Of course, today there are many areas where men and women can fully realize themselves. Health care, education, culture and other areas are equally adequately assessed from the point of view of the possibility of realizing the internal potential of men and women. But even there, hidden gender stereotypes can still be revealed. So, in school education, a teacher of drawing or music is more associated with a woman. Although in real practice we observe the success of men in this role.

In 2018, a study of gender stereotypes was conducted, which made it possible to identify areas of activity with restrictions for women and men (N=361, questionnaire, multistage, random, quota sampling). Thus, for women, restrictions are manifested in industry (47.7% of respondents), transport (39.2%).

Respondents named the physical abilities of women (73%) and their biological predispositions (40.5%) as the main reasons for the restrictions. Note that these reasons are dictated by hidden gender stereotypes.

In relation to men, the distribution turned out to be interesting in that 30.5% of the respondents found it difficult to answer at all. So, a third part of the respondents could not name areas of restriction for men. As restrictions, in 40.5% of cases they named the service sector, some sports, in 30.3% – art and culture, 15.9% – education, 10.7% – science. As you can see, the respondents name other areas in which men could experience restrictions in their careers.

Of course, real practice shows that both men and women can build a career quite successfully in any field of activity. But still, for example, in the sphere of politics or the sphere of air transportation, a woman will be closer watched by society. Thus, Aeroflot employs about 4.2 thousand pilots, of which only 58 are women [9].

Quite interesting data from a sociological study about policewomen. It turned out that women in the police are represented not only in “cabinet” positions and in positions that involve work with children in the juvenile affairs inspectorate, but also in operational units, for example, in the criminal investigation department

[10]. For female police officers, there is a gender-stereotypical “glass ceiling” problem, as intense career advancement seems to be incompatible with mandatory motherhood for women.

A certain interest can also be caused if the kindergarten teacher is a man. In Russia, such an experience is found in Moscow, Tyumen. As a rule, both the men themselves and the social environment during the period of adaptation at the workplace are quite cautious about the profession. However, over time, gender perception is more and more smoothed out [2]. As for other countries, according to official data, in 2017, 35,088 men worked in kindergartens in Germany. This is 5.85% of the total number of employees of preschool institutions [3].

Inference.

Gender affects all spheres of human life and leaves its mark on the thinking and behavior of people. In some cases, its negative effects are obvious, in others they are invisible. But in any case, gender restrictions act as barriers to human life. So, on the one hand, a career is possible in any field, but on the other hand, gender stereotypes often limit people's opportunities, act as barriers to a person's life when they have to live in the circle of gender stereotypes and prove their worth and professionalism.

References

1. Bazhenova, I. S. Gender Aspects of Nonverbal Communication. Summer School "Society and Gender". Ryazan, 2003. <http://www.gender-cent.ryazan.ru/bazhenova.htm>.
2. It would be great if men worked in kindergarten. https://mel.fm/lichny_opyt/5916407-educator_man.
3. Male Educator: Prejudice and Reality. <https://p.dw.com/p/36gav>.
4. Gabrielyan, N. M. “Pop-up Atlantis (meditations on the theme of feminism)”. "Valdai-96": Materials of the First Russian Summer School on Women's and Gender Studies, Moscow, 1997. P. 70-75.
5. Geodakyan, V. A. “About some patterns and phenomena associated with sex”. Probabilistic methods in biology: Sat. scientific Art., edited by V. S. Korolyuk, Kyiv, 1985. P.19-41.
6. Goroshko, E. I. Peculiarities of male and female verbal behavior (psycholinguistic analysis): Ph.D. dis. ... cand. philol. Sciences. Moscow: Russian Academy of Sciences, Institute of Linguistics. 1996. 27 p.
7. Is gender equality achievable in the labor market? <https://novosibirsk.hh.ru/article/26280>.
8. Zemskaya, E. A., Kitaygorodskaya, M. M., Rozanova, N. N. “Features of male and female speech”. Russian language in its functioning. Communicative and pragmatic aspect: Sat. scientific Art., edited by E.A. Zemskoy and D.N. Shmelev, Moscow: Nauka, 1993. P.90-136.
9. Study: Aeroflot and Emirates have the fewest female pilots. <https://newizv.ru/news/world/26-08-2019/issledovanie-menshe-vsego-zhenschin-pilotov-rabotayut-v-aeroflote-i-emirates>.
10. Chemankova, E. D. “Policewomen: how the choice of profession occurs”. Sotsiologicheskkiye issledovaniya. 2019. № 4. P. 126-132.